

Signal Transduction Pathways in *Candida albicans*: A Focus on MAPK regulation during infection

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Mitogen Activated Protein Kinase Pathway (MAPK) in *C. albicans*

A series of signal transduction pathways exist in all fungi that respond to physiological stress and environmental changes (Rispaill et al., 2009). In *C. albicans*, many of these pathways are involved in coordinating yeast-hypha morphogenesis with stress signaling (Shapiro et al., 2011; Huang, 2012). MAP kinase pathways are widely conserved pathways that are involved in the monitoring, amplification, and articulation of stress signals (Navarro-Garcia et al., 2001; Smith et al., 2010). These pathways respond to various environmental stimuli such as osmotic stress, oxidative stress, and the presence of sex pheromones (Figure 1.6). The MAPK pathways in *C. albicans* are divided into levels of the MAPKK kinase (MAPKKK) (Figure 1.6:3), MAP kinase kinase (MAPKK) (Figure 1.6:4), and MAPK (Figure 1.6:5). Membrane proteins and cell wall proteins such as the signaling mucin Msb2, which also have trans-membrane signaling domains (Figure 1.6:2), sense environmental cues leading to activation of protein kinase cascades via the phosphorylation of tyrosine and threonine residues present in their catalytic domains. Then these MAPK activate or deactivate the activity of transcription factors (Figure 1.6:6), which results in specific transcriptional responses to the perceived signal (Biswas et al., 2007; Rispaill et al., 2009).

Hog1 Pathway in *C. albicans*

The MAPK-Hog (high osmolarity glycerol) pathway responds to osmotic and oxidative stress and is also important for resistance to heavy metals (Yin et al., 2009), tolerance to caspofungin (Kelly et al., 2009), regulation of the yeast-hypha transition (Alonso-Monge et al., 1999), chlamydospore formation (Alonso-Monge et al., 2003), cell wall biogenesis (Eisman et al., 2006), progression of the cell cycle (Correia et al., 2010), virulence in animal models, and susceptibility to phagocytes (Arana et al., 2007; Miramon et al., 2012). Therefore, the Hog1 pathway in *C. albicans* plays an important role in responding to a wide range of physiological stimuli and is critical for providing protection to the fungus inside the host (Munro et al., 2007; Kelly et al., 2009; Correia et al., 2010; Gonzalez-Parraga et al., 2010). Inside macrophages and neutrophils, the Hog1 pathway is activated within the phagolysosome during host invasion (Gonzalez-Parraga et al., 2010). The MAPK-Hog1 pathway of *C. albicans* consists of two functional membrane branches, one activated by the membrane sensor Ssu81p and the other by Sln1p (Nagahashi et al., 1998). The Ssk1p is activated when the cell senses high osmolality conditions and is negatively regulated by Sln1 (Nagahashi et al., 1998; Cheetham et al., 2007; Alonso-Monge et al., 2009). The activated Ssk1p binds to Ssk2 and phosphorylates Ssk2, which then phosphorylates Pbs2p, leading to the phosphorylation of Hog1p. Ssu81p and Sln1p sense internal and external osmotic changes, which lead to fungal cell growth and expansion (Chauhan et al., 2006; Kruppa and Calderone, 2006; Monge et al., 2006). It is known from previous studies that the sensors of the Hog1 pathway (*Msb2p* and *Ssu81p*) play important roles in *C. albicans* growth and cell wall construction since mutants lacking these proteins have defects in N-glycosylation and $\beta(1,3)$ glucan biosynthesis (Zucchi et al., 2010;

Cantero and Ernst, 2011). Recently it has also been shown that Cap1 is the transcription factor responding to oxidative stress in *C. albicans* (Kelly et al., 2009).

MKC1 Pathway in *C. albicans*

The activation of the MAPK-Mkc1 pathway in *C. albicans* is partially dependent upon the Hog1 pathway, and this pathway also responds partially to oxidative stress. The *C. albicans* *mkc1* mutant shows no increase in sensitivity upon exposure to oxidative stress (Alonso-Monge et al., 2009). The most important role of this pathway is in regulating cell wall architecture, morphogenesis, formation of biofilms, and virulence (Roman et al., 2009). The membrane sensors of this pathway (*Wscp* and *Mid1p*) are activated in response to changing environmental conditions that lead to cell wall stretch, which further activates Rho1p and the downstream protein kinase C (*Pkc1*). This phosphorylates Mkc1p, which finally activates downstream transcription factors such as Rlm1 (Munro et al., 2007; Rispaill et al., 2009). Both the Mkc1 and Hog1 pathways respond to external changes in environments and changes in local osmotic solute concentration (Gonzalez-Parraga et al., 2010). It was also shown that the MAPK-Mkc1 pathway is activated during *C. albicans* growth in agar matrices (Zucchi et al., 2010).

Cek1 Pathway in *C. albicans*

In *C. albicans*, the MAPK-Cek1 pathway plays an important role in virulence and morphogenesis. Inactivation of this pathway caused by mutations has shown defects in invasive growth, cell wall architecture, and virulence (Galan-Diez et al., 2010). *C. albicans* *cek1* mutants are hypersensitive to cell wall perturbing agents, indicating the role of this pathway in cell wall biosynthesis (Galan-Diez et al., 2010). The Cek1 pathway is also implicated in immune evasion by showing that *cek1*

mutants display enhanced exposure of β -1,3 glucan, leading to greater phagocytosis upon interaction with macrophages and dendritic cells (Galan-Diez et al., 2010).

An important plasma membrane protein covalently bound to the cell wall is termed Dfi1. It is activated upon contact with semi-solid surfaces, which further activates the MAPK-Cek1 pathway leading to filamentous growth. It has also been shown that Dfi1 confers resistance to drugs affecting cell wall integrity (Zucchi et al., 2010). During nutrient starvation, elements of this pathway are activated including Cst20p, Hst7p, Cek1p, and the transcription factor Cph1p—one of several transcription factors involved in regulating hypha formation (Csank et al., 1998). This pathway also plays an important role in invasive candidiasis leading to invasion of epithelial and endothelial cells, consequently initiating candidemia. The presence of quorum sensing molecules also leads to phosphorylation of Cek1p and Mkc1p (Roman et al., 2009). Interestingly, filamentation can occur without Cek1p presence, indicating other pathways involved in upregulating this process. The MAPK-Cek1 and cAMP/PKA pathways regulate filamentous growth by activating downstream transcription factors Rlm1, Cph1, and Efg1 (reviewed in Gow et al., 2011; Calderone and Clancy, 2012).

Figure 1. 6 Mitogen Activated Protein Kinase pathways (MAPK) in *C. albicans*.

References

- Alonso-Monge, R., et al. (1999). "The role of high osmolarity glycerol response pathway during yeast-hyphal transition." *Molecular Microbiology*, 33(3), 234-243.
- Alonso-Monge, R., et al. (2003). "Chlamyospore formation mediated by high osmolarity glycerol response." *Fungal Genetics and Biology*, 39(3), 213-221.
- Biswas, S.K., et al. (2007). "Role of MAP kinases during stress response." *Fungal Genetics Reports*, Vol.54.
- Cheetham, S.W., et al. (2007). "Regulation of osmoregulatory signaling pathways." *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, Vol.282.
- Csank, C.L., et al. (1998). "The role of MAPK-Cek signaling during morphogenesis." *Microbiology*, Vol.144.

- Eisman, B.E., et al. (2006). "Cell wall biogenesis regulated by MAPK pathways." *Fungal Genetics Reports*, Vol.53.
- Galan-Diez, M., et al. (2010). "The role of Cek pathways during immune evasion." *PLoS ONE*, Vol.5.
- Gonzalez-Parraga, P., et al. (2010). "Responses to osmotic changes mediated by MAPK pathways." *Fungal Biology Reviews*, Vol.24.
- Munro, C.A., & Gow N.R.(2007). "Role of Hog pathways during host invasion." *Nature Reviews Microbiology*, Vol.(5).
- Navarro-Garcia F.E.V.O.(20001) "Conserved mitogen activated protein kinases." *Fungal Genetics Reports* Vol.(48).
- Rispaill N.(2009) "Signaling mechanisms during fungal responses." *Fungal Genetics Reports* Vol.(56).
- Smith J.(2010) "MAP kinase signaling mechanisms." *Fungal Genetics Reports* Vol.(54).
- Zucchi T.I.(2010) "Cell wall biosynthesis regulated by Hog pathways." *Fungal Genetics Reports* Vol.(52).